

Report on the Third Regenerative medicine workshop

Mariana Pacheco Blanco, Yevhen Horokhovatskyi, Kristin Saar, Kristin Aldag

Introduction: Gilles Weder, CSEM and Mariana Pacheco Blanco, AMIRES

According to Chat GPT, regenerative medicine (RegMed) aims to repair, replace or regenerate damaged or diseased tissues or organs. Three main topics are covered in RegMed:

- 1) **Gene therapy**, which currently has high costs, but if successful can considerably improve the quality of life of patients.
- 2) **Cell therapy**, which revolutionized cancer treatment, but manufacturing is still a challenge.
- 3) **Tissue engineering**, the use of cells and biomaterials, which currently are lagging in adoption.

During the event that took place on June 1, 2023, in Prague, the discussion was centred in the convergence between biology and technology, and how enabling technologies can be valorised for regenerative medicine – in other words, how great ideas can reach the patient in clinical practice. Many new approaches e.g. reuse of telecommunication materials for cell sorting systems, or bioreactors, not yet used in the medical field, are promising solutions.

The workshop was structured around an opening keynote speech, followed by 3 dedicated sessions:

- 1) Outcomes and challenges of four EU-funded projects.
- 2) Discussion and opinions of clinical needs in regenerative medicine.
- 3) Presentation of enabling technologies from three companies and a technology provider.

In order to facilitate collaborations and direct future research, the participants were introduced three upcoming funding calls for RegMed-related proposals in the public funding programme Horizon Europe:

- Innovative non-animal human-based tools and strategies for biomedical research ([HORIZON-HLTH-2024-TOOL-05-06-two-stage](#))
- Bio-printing of living cells for regenerative medicine ([HORIZON-HLTH-2024-TOOL-11-02](#))
- Advanced biomaterials for the Health Care (IA) ([HORIZON-CL4-2024-RESILIENCE-01-36](#))

It is a fact, that Europe is still behind other regions of the world in RegMed, e.g. in terms of clinical trials and investments. Nevertheless, we can witness a steady increase of the number of publications in RegMed field, despite light decrease in recent years due to pandemic.

KEYNOTE PRESENTATION: Unmet needs in post ischemic cardiac regeneration and awakening revisited: how the brains survive 60 minutes of cardiac arrest/resuscitation

Jan Bělohávek, General University Hospital and the First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Czech Republic.

Overall, the number of patients of cardiac failure is increasing, making an “epidemic of heart failure”, while their mortality is decreasing due to sophisticated treatment options. Despite decreasing mortality, up to 50% of patients die; – this is comparable to lives lost to oncological diseases. The incidence of acute myocardial infarction cardiogenic shock (AMI-CS) and non-AMI-CS are increasing. Thanks to the technology boom in the last 10 years, we can substitute for organs in acute patients. For instance, Prof. Belohlavek’s team is able to provide external perfusion of main organs, e.g. heart, kidney, liver. An example was a patient in Intensive Care Unit, who was connected to extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) device for 10+ days before his heart restarted. Nevertheless, chronic heart diseases are still a concern. Cardiac recovery is possible, and we see it often after successful intervention, but it is not equivalent to regeneration. Clinical experiences show that most interventions

fail. In fact, doing too much can harm the patient. Usually, patients' heart condition is continuously declining, and their quality of life deteriorates even if the patient survives. Cardiogenic shock is very heterogenous, and single interventions rarely make a difference on a large scale. Therapies need to be tested in adequate populations, which are not easy to identify. For instance, a cohort of patients could be the “easy patients”, which survive even without external effort. Others will die no matter what, and only 12-25% of patients are candidate for mechanical circulatory support intervention. Four key concepts of possible heart regeneration in RegMed exist: 1) Renewal of pre-existing cardiomyocytes, 2) Cell therapy, 3) Reprogramming of non-cardiomyocytes into cardiomyocytes, and 4) Engineered cardiac tissue. The main principle is the re-entry of cell cycle and differentiation, the goal is the redevelopment of cells into new cardiomyocytes. However, research shows that adult stem cells from bone marrow do not become cardiomyocytes, and direct reprogramming of cardio fibroblasts is not very efficient. Trials on cardiac repair using stem cells following myocardial infarction show that it is not clear whether the therapy was effective or whether it was just natural progression of the disease. Other approaches have been evaluated but are not yet effective. For instance, a meta-analysis of 80 randomised clinical trials (RCT) using bone marrow-derived cells in the heart with thousands of patients showed no significant improvement. With up to 75 RCT and 11 systematic reviews published every day in the topic, it is near impossible to stay oriented in the research. We know that immediate intervention and resuscitation is necessary and the setting matters. Overall, only 10% of cardiac arrest patients survive, which varies greatly between EU countries. Time is key for survival: after 15 minutes of continuous resuscitation, the chances of survival decrease to 2%. With a very invasive approach of using extracorporeal cardiopulmonary resuscitation (ECPR) external device that substitutes the heart, survival is significantly higher compared to using traditional methods. In conclusion, new methods may help patients to survive prolonged cardiac arrest. However, sometimes we are saving the brain but not the heart. There is potential for regeneration, but more research is needed.

EU-FUNDED PROJECTS & OPPORTUNITIES

In total, 14 projects were funded from the call [H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020](#) *Regenerative medicine: from new insights to new applications*. Four of them were represented in the workshop.

ORGANTRANS: bioprinted liver tissue engineering as new alternative to chronic liver patients, presented by Gilles Weder, Head Research & Business Development Life Sciences Technologies, CSEM, Switzerland. This project addresses the growing need for liver transplants, which are the only effective treatment for various liver diseases, causing 2 million deaths annually worldwide. Only 10% of transplantation needs are currently met. Targeting chronic end-stage liver diseases and residual healthy tissues, ORGANTRANS combines autonomous self-assembly with biomimicry. The project relies on organoid technologies as building blocks, complemented by bioprinting for the recreation of the architecture of the tissue for vascularisation. The vascularisation strategy is based on infusion and inclusion, and it has been the biggest challenge of the project.

AMELIE: autologous skeletal muscle derived cells to restore the function of the sphincter muscle, presented by Chara Simitzi, Postdoctoral Research Scientist in the Division of Medicine, University College London, England. Obstetric sphincter injury occurs in 5.5% of postpartum women, however, current surgical management is not appropriate for all patients. AMELIE is developing a novel tissue engineered product consisting of autologous skeletal muscle cells attached to thermally induced phase separation (TIPS) microspheres for the treatment of obstetric trauma induced incontinence. Autologous skeletal muscle derived cells (ASMDC) provide an appropriate source of skeletal muscle cells for delivery into the defective external anal sphincter. The central hypothesis of the project is that ASMDC combined with biodegradable, implantable microcarriers provides a safe and beneficial new product to improve the effectiveness of regenerative medicine for incontinence. The consortium is

currently on non-clinical studies phase, which includes safety testing and the formulation of the solution.

PREMSTEM: New regenerative stem cell therapy to repair the brain damage caused by premature birth, presented by Cindy Bokobza, Postdoctoral Research Scientist in the Lab of Neurodiderot Gressens, INSERM, France. Every year, 15 million babies are delivered prematurely. While it is the first cause of death in new-borns and can result in long-term sequels and disability, the therapeutic options are scarce. PREMSTEM project evaluates human mesenchymal stem cells (HuMSCs) to repair the preterm brain. In addition to migration capacity and regenerative properties, these cells are immunosuppressive, anti-inflammatory and enable relatively simple and minimally invasive access via the umbilical cord. By testing different doses, routes, and timing of naive HuMSC, the PREMSTEM consortium aims to determine the optimal neuroprotective paradigm. Current results indicate HuMSCs work better when administrated by the intranasal route long after inflammatory insults.

JOINTPROMISE: complex joint implants containing biological information to effectuate the regeneration, presented by Isaak Decoene, Senior Researcher in Skeletal Biology and Engineering Research Center, KU Leuven, Belgium. Joint defect treatment does not exist, leading to permanent regeneration for the time being. The project is setting up an end-to-end automation platform for the manufacture of complex organoid-based implants. Moreover, manual processes in ATMP manufacture led to high costs, long production times and moderate chances of success. JOINTPROMISE takes a bottom-up strategy to combine different types of tissues in one implant. It combines robust biologic building blocks (μ tissues) to build living implants able to restore joint function with automated capacity designed for bottom-up tissue product biomanufacture. The novel organoid based ATMP manufacturing platform developed in the project can also be deployed for generic use.

CLINICAL NEEDS

During this session, Kateřina Růžičková, Clinical Research Associate at BIOINOVA, Czech Republic, presented **Clinical applications of stem cells in cartilage regeneration**. Bioinov, founded in 2008 as an academic spin-off, is certified as a laboratory and manufacturer of advanced medicinal products (ATMPs) and medical devices for diagnostics. The company offers ATMP-based on autologous expanded mesenchymal stem cells from bone marrow. Two products offered by the company are still under clinical trials: BiCure ortho™ (currently phase II efficacy assessment) and BiCure ophtalmo™ (currently close to clinical testing phase I). Patient questionnaires are collected before surgery, and at 6, 12 and 24 months after surgery. Results for both trials are still pending. Enrolling the necessary number of patients in the trials and following up with them is the biggest challenge.

Daniel Scherman, Director of the Foundation of Rare Diseases and founder of the “Paris Centre of Pharmaceutical Research” at the Paris Pharmacy Faculty, and of the “Laboratory of Chemical and Biological Tools for Health” (UTCBS), France presented the talk **Non viral gene therapy using optimized plasmid devoid of antibiotic resistance gene and physical gene delivery**. He explained the alternative methods of non-viral gene therapies, such as the use of biosafe plasmids, which are DNA circular molecules that can be easily manipulated. The use of plasmids is widely spread for several decades, however their use in recent years for cell therapies research had increased. For instance, their use should accelerate the clinical implementation and enhance the biosafety of CAR-T therapy, among other applications. He also presented the activities from the Foundation of Rare diseases, in which they organise massive open online courses (MOOCs). In these courses, people can learn about the diagnosis of rare diseases, translational research, innovative therapy, and personalised medicine.

The last talk of this session, **HTA for regenerative medicine and regulatory aspects**, was given by Petra Maresova, and Lukáš Peter, Co-owner and CEO of Betthera, and Regulatory Affairs and Medical Device Legislation Expert at Betthera respectively, Czech Republic. Betthera offers services such as Budget impact analysis, Cost benefit analyses, Health Technology Assessment (HTA), reimbursement models

as well as consulting on regulatory affairs for medical devices, drugs, ATMPs and regulatory strategy preparation. From 2025, part of HTA will be compulsory for drug development and clinical trials in the EU (EU HTA regulation 2021/2282). Betthera is compliant with this methodology. In order to provide a complete HTA, the following aspects should be considered adjusted to the phase of development: health problem and the current use of the technology to solve it (size of the market and costs), safety assessment, clinical effectiveness (measure of quality of life), economic evaluation (using measures such as QALY or quality-adjusted life year, ICER or incremental cost effectiveness ration), ethical, legal, patient and social aspects. The consideration of regulatory aspects can improve the design and development process, thereby increasing competitiveness of medical devices, if this is properly done. Initially, setting a regulatory strategy is essential to optimise processes, money, time and energy to bring a product to the market. This also includes processes of management, training, designing, packaging, etc. In this step, the risk class should be identified as well as the necessary tests and requirements. Lastly, there are requirements such as post market clinical evaluation, clinical investigation plan etc. Betthera offers services in both EU regulation and the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) compliance requirements.

ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

Revolutionizing wound care: the time is now for cell therapies to hit the market, presented by Federico Figliolini, R&D manager at HEALIVA, Switzerland. With 60% of chronic wounds currently remaining unhealed, HEALIVA aims to provide affordable personalised solutions for hard-to-heal wounds, including cell therapies and medical devices. Cellular therapy in wound healing provides new opportunities for rapid and effective healing at a lower cost and enables easier scale up of production. Their portfolio addresses the entire spectrum of the wound-care process for chronic wounds, from first steps to the completion of closure.

Ioanna Theochari, Biochemist at PhosPrint, Greece, presented **Transforming healthcare: laser bioprinting advances in regenerative medicine**. PhosPrint is a spin-off developing high-quality lasers. The company has pre-industrial laser bioprinter and protocols to isolate, expand and print cells during surgery. The first clinical application of the technology is neobladder construction for bladder cancer patients undergoing cystectomy to overcome the adverse events and high costs related to current standard of care.

Medicinal signalling cells for liver regenerative medicine presented by Etienne Sokal, Professor of Medicine and CEO of the Cellaion, Belgium. Cellaion company focuses on stem cell based regenerative liver therapy, in which freshly isolated hepatocytes can engraft and bring de novo missing enzyme activities. The first target is life-threatening liver diseases. Phase II 2A study in patients was successful and company has the aim to reach conditional approval as there is no treatment currently available.

The last talk of the session and of the day, **Tools for regenerative medicine**, was given by Thomas Valentin, Group Leader of Automated Sample Handling at CSEM, Switzerland. CSEM is a public-private non-profit developing and transferring world-class technologies to industry. The centre has two main work streams: applied research through public funding and tech transfer via direct industry mandates, following a full cost model. The main technologies CSEM is active in include Digital Technologies, Precision Manufacturing and Sustainable Energies. For life sciences, CSEM provides three main types of tools: Automated cell microsystems, Biomonitoring and Lab automation & AI. In the field of regenerative medicine, this includes automation, closed systems and smart labware.

These consortia, research organisations and companies provided insights into the potential of the current research in regenerative medicine, which aims to fill the needs of patients for improving their lives, in survival and quality of life. After this day of inspiring talks, we found a convergence between biology and technology, and how great ideas reach the patient in clinical practice.